

CUMULATIVE DISSERTATION

More Than Medicine: The Unseen Aftermath of Childhood Cancer

Understanding non-medical challenges that affect childhood cancer patients,
survivors and their parents throughout the cancer trajectory

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ABSTRACT

Background: This dissertation aimed to gain a better understanding of the administrative, practical, and socio-bureaucratic hardships associated with childhood cancer, with a particular focus on survivorship. Specifically, the objectives were to (1) understand employment changes among parents of children diagnosed with cancer and examine potential long-term impacts, (2) enhance the understanding of the accessibility of care for survivors attending long-term follow-up (LTFU) care, and (3) to provide a comprehensive overview of insurance, legal, and financial hardships faced by survivors.

Methods: A registry-based questionnaire study was conducted to explore parents' employment changes and predict long-term impacts. Accessibility of long-term follow-up care among survivors was investigated using a quantitative cohort study linked to index data. Existing evidence on insurance, legal, and financial hardships experienced by survivors was synthesized in a systematic literature review.

Results: Employment changes during their child's cancer treatment were common, however most parents did not report lasting financial or professional impacts. For most survivors, the LTFU clinic was reachable within reasonable travel time, and travel time was not associated with health status. Survivors, however, face many long-term, interrelated socio-bureaucratic hardships, resulting in problems with the affordability of care.

Conclusions: The impact of childhood cancer on survivors' health, as well as its interplay with their and their parents' socio-economic situation and socio-bureaucratic and practical challenges, is multifaceted and reciprocally influences survivors' health and well-being. This dissertation advocates for the provision of appropriate, targeted and continuous support in all domains of need and calls for collaborative efforts from research, policy and practice in addressing these needs.

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List of abbreviations

CACS	Childhood and adolescent cancer survivors
CCS	Childhood cancer survivors
CIMD	Canadian Index of Multiple Deprivation
CNS	Central nervous system
COG	Children's Oncology Group
DI	Disability insurance
EO	Income Compensation Ordinance (Erwerbsersatzordnung)
HINT	Health insurance navigation tool
HRQOL	Health-related quality of life
ICCC-3	International Classification of Childhood Cancer, Third Edition
KiKR	Childhood Cancer Registry (Kinderkrebsregister)
LTFU	Long-term follow-up
LTSC	Long Term Survivor Clinic
LTSQ	Long Term Survivor Questionnaire
PanCare	Pan-European Network for Care of Survivors after Childhood and Adolescent Cancer
PAT	Psychosocial Assessment Tool
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
PROSPERO	Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews
PSCPCC	Psychosocial Standards of Care Project for Childhood Cancer
SDI	Socio-demographic index
SDOH	Social Determinants of Health
WHO	World Health Organization

1 INTRODUCTION AND MAIN OBJECTIVE

Childhood and adolescent cancers are rare, yet they remain among the leading causes of mortality in this age group worldwide, despite substantial advancements in survival rates^{1,2}. In most cases, childhood cancer does not have a known cause and is generally not preventable or identifiable through screening². Prevention efforts are therefore not as advisable and effective as for adult cancers. The focus should instead be on preventing secondary cancers, fostering healthy behaviors, and monitoring late effects².

Survival rates have increased to over 80% in countries with high socio-demographic indices and continue to rise globally¹. This rise brings new challenges for pediatric oncologists and all healthcare professionals and caregivers involved in caring for children and adolescents living with cancer. It is important to recognize that the conclusion of treatment does not necessarily mark the end of cancer^{3,4}.

Late effects of cancer and its treatment are common, prompting a shift in medical and research focus towards survivorship and its associated challenges^{5,6}. Survivor-specific follow-up care aims to monitor the long-term effects to ensure early detection and opportunities for care to help improve both survival and health-related quality of life⁷. In addition to the physical and psychological consequences, survivors of childhood cancer are confronted with challenges related to education and employment, as well as insurance, legal, and financial difficulties^{8,9}. Socio-bureaucratic hardships and administrative and practical challenges accompany the cancer trajectory⁹⁻¹¹.

Childhood cancer does not only affect the patient but impacts the entire family. Parents are particularly challenged with managing all aspects of their child's illness, which not only results in a disruption of everyday life, but can also impact their professional and financial circumstances, with potentially long-lasting consequences¹²⁻¹⁴.

In order to provide adequate support and resources for survivors and their families, it is crucial to understand the challenges they are facing and their respective needs in detail. The overall objective of this dissertation is therefore to gain a better understanding of the administrative, practical and socio-bureaucratic hardships associated with childhood cancer, with a particular focus on survivorship.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Childhood cancer

Cancer describes the uncontrolled proliferation and growth of cells, i.e., malignant tissue formation (malignant neoplasia) or a malignant tumor (cancerous tumor, malignoma)¹⁵. The term “malignant” denotes not only uncontrolled cell proliferation, but also the subsequent metastases (spread of the cancer) and invasion into healthy tissue¹⁶. There are over a hundred types of cancer¹⁶.

Childhood cancer describes cancer diagnosed in children between the ages of 0-14 years, often expanded to include adolescents between the ages of 15-19 years^{1,17}. Unlike adult cancers, where classification is based on the location of the tumor, childhood cancer is based on the morphology of the tumor¹⁸. The third edition of the International Classification of Childhood Cancer (ICCC-3) categorizes childhood cancers into 12 diagnostic main groups and 47 diagnostic subgroups^{18,19}:

- I. Leukemias, myeloproliferative diseases, and myelodysplastic diseases
- II. Lymphomas and reticuloendothelial neoplasms
- III. Central nervous system (CNS) and miscellaneous intracranial and intraspinal neoplasms
- IV. Neuroblastoma and other peripheral nervous cell tumors
- V. Retinoblastoma
- VI. Renal tumors
- VII. Hepatic tumors
- VIII. Malignant bone tumors
- IX. Soft tissue and other extraosseous sarcomas
- X. Germ cell tumors, trophoblastic tumors, and neoplasms of gonads
- XI. Other malignant epithelial neoplasms and malignant melanomas
- XII. Other and unspecified malignant neoplasms

Cancer in children and adolescents is rare. Globally, childhood cancers account for just 1% of all cancers diagnosed each year¹. In Switzerland, where around 350 children and adolescents are diagnosed with cancer each year, it is 4%²⁰. The most frequent types of cancer in children (0-14 years

of age) are leukemias, brain and other CNS tumors, and lymphomas^{17,21}. In adolescents (15-19 years of age), the next most frequent diagnoses subsequent to these three cancers are germ cell tumors and certain carcinomas and melanomas^{17,21}. Some diagnoses may be more prevalent in either girls or boys, or across different age demographics²¹.

2.2 Childhood cancer treatment and survival

For children and adolescents, cancer is still a leading cause of death, however, when identified early and treated adequately, the likelihood of survival is high². Even though survival varies by cancer type, most are curable today⁵. *Treatment* options include surgery, drug therapies such as chemotherapy, immunotherapy, hematopoietic stem cell transplantation, or radiation therapy²². The choice of treatment depends primarily on the type of cancer and how widespread it is, as well as patient characteristics. Often, a combination of different therapies is used²². Treatment for childhood cancer is usually provided in specialized *pediatric oncology* centers, based on international protocols²³. International and interdisciplinary study groups strive to continuously optimize treatments^{23,24}. Over the last two decades, oncological treatment protocols have increasingly incorporated risk stratification based on tumor biology and disease extent²⁵. For patients with localized, biologically favorable malignancies, treatment intensity has been substantially modified to reduce the risk of treatment-related complications. In contrast, patients with high-risk or advanced-stage cancers receive more intensive treatment regimens to optimize disease control and long-term survival²⁵.

As *survival* rates continue to improve, the number of childhood cancer patients who will become childhood cancer *survivors* is growing^{3,24}. The term childhood cancer *survivors* (hereinafter referred to as “survivors”) describes former patients who were diagnosed with cancer in childhood (and adolescence) and are alive for at least two years after diagnosis²⁶. From five years after diagnosis, they are usually referred to as *long-term survivors*²⁷.

Survival rates for childhood cancer have improved considerably over the last decades. Due to the advancements in pediatric oncology, survival rates are over 80% in high-income countries and continue to rise globally^{1,24}. Survival rates, however, have not improved equally in all parts of the

world⁵. In countries with a low socio-demographic index (SDI; a composite indicator of development status strongly correlated with health outcomes), it is estimated that approximately half of children with cancer go undiagnosed and therefore untreated^{28,29}. The survival rate in these countries is substantially lower, at approximately 30% in comparison to countries with a high SDI³⁰.

Irrespective of the country's wealth and health expenditure, evidence is growing that poorer survival and health outcomes are also associated with individual non-medical factors, such as the family's socio-economic situation^{31,32}. Socio-economic differences in overall mortality from childhood cancer have been observed even in countries with mandatory health insurance, universal healthcare, and mostly equal access to healthcare services³³⁻³⁶. Certain families therefore appear to be at an unfair disadvantage compared to others.

2.3 Childhood cancer as a family matter

Adjusting to a child's cancer diagnosis poses significant challenges for the whole family. Treating and caring for pediatric cancer patients is resource-intensive, with significant implications for families' physical, emotional and financial well-being³⁷.

The treatment of childhood cancer is often complex, intensive, and potentially lengthy. In addition to the many new caregiving responsibilities that come with a childhood cancer diagnosis, daily life is often taken over by frequent hospital visits, scheduling appointments, gathering documents, and navigating bureaucratic demands, such as insurance claims and applications for financial support¹⁰. Compared to parents of healthy children, parents of children with chronic illnesses, including cancer, have been found to experience higher levels of parenting stress, i.e., stress related to the role as parent^{38,39}. Higher parenting stress was found to be associated with greater parental responsibility for treatment management³⁹. A meta-analysis found that stress levels vary depending on factors such as the severity and duration of the illness, the child's age, parental gender and mental health, marital status and quality of marriage, and levels of perceived support³⁸. Access to healthcare services and support systems, whether private or governmental, may partly determine parents' ability to balance different responsibilities when their child is diagnosed with cancer⁴⁰.

2.4 Parental employment disruptions during diagnosis and treatment of childhood cancer

With parents having to adapt to a number of new roles,⁴¹ the act of balancing familial responsibilities, caring for a child suffering from a severe medical condition, and professional obligations is extremely demanding^{40,42-45}. As indicated in existing research, parents of children with cancer have reported significant challenges in combining work with caring for their ill child and other family members^{40,42-46}. These challenges are often compounded by substantial disruptions to their daily lives.

Restructuring of roles and responsibilities, both within the family and in the professional setting, is inevitable, with mothers often taking primary responsibility for the ill child^{43,44,47-49}. These shifts can lead to employment disruptions⁴⁷. Treatment-related employment disruptions, including unpaid leave, reduced workloads, alterations to work schedules, or quitting altogether, are common among parents of children with cancer^{47,48,50}. Some studies report that up to 94% of families are affected by some sort of employment disruption resulting from the child's cancer^{51,52}. In addition to work disruptions, parents have also been shown to experience substantial socio-economic consequences, such as income losses and increased out-of-pocket expenses^{47,53}. Along with medical expenses, parents incur substantial non-medical expenses for meals, transportation, and accommodation during treatment⁵⁴⁻⁵⁶, leading to a financial burden for families^{47,51,52,56}. Financial burden, in turn, is another source of psychosocial stress for parents, which can manifest itself in symptoms such as anxiety, distress, and disrupted sleep⁵⁷. Psychological, family, and practical factors influence parents' ability to remain at work and/or return to work^{40,45,46,56}.

The biggest changes in role dynamics usually occur in the early stages of diagnosis and initial treatment^{43,45}. However, survivors are often subject to a range of adverse late effects⁵⁸, creating care demands that may continue well beyond the end of treatment and extend into the survivorship phase^{45,46,59}. As the primary informal caregivers to their children, it is crucial that parents' experiences of balancing parenting and work are understood, particularly as caregiving demands persist. Even though distress levels decrease with time after diagnosis, some parents report ongoing distress⁸. Persistent challenges associated with coping with increased care needs and disruption to work life are possible, as are long-term socio-economic consequences⁴⁷. However, there has been a lack of studies

helping to understand the long-term professional and financial repercussions that extend well beyond the end of treatment into long-term survival.

RESEARCH GAP 1

While existing research provides valuable insights into how parents of children with cancer adapt to their new roles and experience employment disruptions, gaps remain in studies investigating long-term repercussions of these disruptions that persist well into their child's survivorship.

2.5 Treatment-related late effects

As survival rates in childhood cancer continue to improve, increasing attention is being paid to both immediate and long-term health impacts of treatment^{1,24}. Due to the highly effective, yet aggressive treatments for childhood cancer, the risk of treatment-related toxicities and health problems is high^{3,24}. Some of these are imminent, like hair loss or vomiting during the active phase of cancer treatment. Others may only emerge after the completion of therapy or even decades later and manifest as *late effects* of cancer and its treatment^{7,60}. Common late effects include the development of secondary malignancies, cardiotoxicity, nephrotoxicity, ototoxicity, bone necrosis, endocrinological deficits, fertility problems, neuro- and psychological problems, and fatigue^{3,6,8,24,61,62}. The risk of developing chronic health conditions is increased⁶¹. By the age of 45, survivors of childhood cancer have twice the disease burden as compared to the general population⁶¹.

Treatment-related late effects can vary in degree and severity, but approximately 60 to 80% of survivors experience at least one late effect⁶¹. For 25%, the complication will be severe or life-threatening^{25,58,63}. Not all survivors are at similar risk of experiencing treatment-related late effects²⁵. In general, the risk is directly proportional to the treatment intensity required to achieve and maintain disease control²⁵. The type of cancer treatment and the age of the child at the time of treatment are also decisive factors in the risk of late effects²⁵.

2.6 Survivorship follow-up care

Given the wide range of potential late effects, the emphasis has transitioned towards optimizing healthcare and improving the quality of life for survivors who are confronted with late effects⁶⁴. To ensure opportunities for adequate care through early detection, monitoring of cancer-related long-term effects is crucial⁶⁰. *Long-term follow-up* (LTFU) care is becoming increasingly important^{7,25}. Screening for early detection of late effects in at-risk survivors with the goal of improving both survival and health-related quality of life (HRQOL) is recommended by various survivorship guidelines^{60,65,66}. For instance, the International Late Effects of Childhood Cancer Guideline Harmonization Group's (IGHG) develops harmonized evidence-based surveillance guidelines for childhood, adolescent, and young adult cancer survivors⁶⁶. Other relevant recommendations are included in the PanCareFollowUp Recommendations (Pan-European Network for Care of Survivors after Childhood and Adolescent Cancer), developed by a broad-based working group comprising late effects specialists, researchers, and survivor representatives for topics not yet addressed by the IGHG⁶⁷. International guidelines are important to provide equal access to high-quality, evidence-based survivorship care.

The Children's Oncology Group (COG; the world's largest organization devoted exclusively to pediatric cancer research), recommends life-long, personalized, risk-based LTFU care for all former pediatric cancer patients who received treatment to prevent, identify, and manage late effects^{25,60}. The COG recommends that survivors receive this care starting two years after completing cancer treatment²⁵. While initial cancer treatment is typically provided at specialized pediatric oncology centers, models of LTFU care delivery vary. The most common model is LTFU care delivered at a cancer center, such as a pediatric oncology clinic, a medical oncology clinic, or a LTFU clinic⁶⁵. Other models are LTFU care led by the primary care physician (community-based care) and shared care between the treatment hospital and a local hospital or primary care physician⁶⁵. The model and type of LTFU care required may differ depending on the potential late effects²⁵. In addition, health counseling and the promotion of healthy lifestyles are important aspects of LTFU care, helping to

reduce the risk of physical and emotional health problems commonly experienced in adulthood²⁵. Relevant recommendations are, for instance, included in the PanCareFollowUp Recommendations⁶⁷. Despite the importance, adherence remains below the levels recommended by healthcare professionals. Some reports suggest that almost half of treated patients are lost to follow-up⁶⁸⁻⁷². The proportion of survivors receiving survivor-focused LTFU care decreases with increasing time from cancer diagnosis²⁵.

2.7 Barriers to survivorship long-term follow-up care

Potential barriers to survivorship LTFU care are manifold. Some issues, such as the lack of clinical practical guidelines for certain clinically relevant late effects, are being addressed by ongoing projects and working groups in an effort to address key issues regarding LTFU care for childhood and adolescent cancer survivors, harmonize evidence-based recommendations, and facilitate the implementation of LTFU care^{65,67}. However, barriers to LTFU care remain a concern.

Previous studies have examined disparities in survivorship care by considering patient-level factors such as race/ethnicity, insurance status and rurality⁷³⁻⁷⁷. However, the impact of these factors has varied across single-site cohort studies⁷³⁻⁷⁸. A recent systematic review identified factors such as employment status, income, education, cancer-related characteristics, sex, and geographical area as potentially influencing engagement and transition to LTFU⁷⁹. But it was asserted that these warrant further investigation⁷⁹.

In certain countries, universal health insurance coverage has removed many barriers to receiving quality healthcare⁸⁰. Nevertheless, geographical location and distance to the clinic remain potential barriers to access to care⁸¹. Place of residence has been associated with health status, health behaviors, and use of health services⁸⁰. Disparities in access to care between living in rural versus urban areas persist⁷¹, with studies showing that the odds of clinic attendance were lower for childhood cancer survivors living further from the clinic⁸².

RESEARCH GAP 2

Inconsistencies in existing research highlight the need for further insights into the impact of travel time, and indirectly, accessibility of follow-up care on the health status of survivors, in order to identify potential barriers to follow-up care.

2.8 Social, economic, and socio-bureaucratic hardships

Many survivors cope well with the health-related late effects associated with childhood cancer. However, there are many who are affected by a different set of difficulties. The consequences of cancer and its treatment can also adversely affect the psychosocial sphere, resulting in negative impacts on family and peer relationships, educational attainment (both formal learning and practical knowledge gained from real-world experience), vocational opportunities, employment prospects, and access to insurance and healthcare^{3,25,83–86}.

Navigating the healthcare and social security system is challenging, even more so for those affected by childhood cancer^{87,88}. Survivors are at risk for adverse socio-economic consequences and socio-bureaucratic burdens^{5,89}. As a consequence of cancer survivors may face difficulties obtaining and maintaining insurance^{11,90,91} and are often subject to higher premiums^{92,93}. In addition, many report increased out-of-pocket medical expenses^{94,95}, difficulty paying for medical care or even delaying or forgoing medical care due to costs^{96,97}. This financial strain and distress, also referred to as “financial toxicity”, can affect both survivors and their families^{98,99}.

Other burdens include being dependent on social security or disability benefits¹⁰⁰ and facing discrimination and limited access to public services¹⁰¹. This can include more difficult access to appropriate education, employment, rehabilitation, dental plans, disability benefits, and insurance¹⁰¹.

These types of hardships are shown to potentially exacerbate or cause physical and psychological harm to survivors, including stress, anxiety, or impaired sleep^{90,95,102}. Physical and psychological late effects associated with childhood cancer may, on the other hand, further contribute to insurance, legal

or financial hardships. Likewise, risk factors such as low income, pre-existing financial difficulties, unemployment, or lack of a social network can increase the risk of encountering these hardships^{96,102-104}.

Insurance, legal, and financial hardships are three distinct but also interrelated types of hardships. Examining them as intertwined and mutually influencing matters, rather than separately, is crucial to achieving a better understanding of the broader picture of these socio-bureaucratic hardships experienced by childhood cancer survivors and associated risk factors.

RESEARCH GAP 3

Existing research shows that survivors face insurance, legal, and financial hardships, however, there is a lack of a comprehensive overview of the existing evidence that considers the interrelatedness of these factors.

3 OBJECTIVES AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The objectives and research questions to be answered, based on the research gaps previously outlined, are as follows:

STUDY 1

The aim of study 1 was to understand employment changes of parents during their child's cancer diagnosis and treatment in Switzerland, and to examine whether impacts persist into survivorship. Specifically, investigated was (1) if and what kind of employment changes occurred in parents during their child's cancer diagnosis and treatment, (2) reasons for the employment changes, (3) differences between mothers and fathers, and (4) if parents experience long-term professional or financial impact due to their child's past illness.

STUDY 2

The objective of study 2 was to enhance the understanding of the accessibility of care for childhood cancer survivors who attend LTFU visits at Long Term Survivor Clinic (LTSC) at the Alberta Children's Hospital in Calgary. Specifically, the objectives were to 1) determine survivors' travel time to reach the LTSC for LTFU visits, and to examine the health status of those attending, and 2) explore the association between travel time and health status, including the role of socio-economic situation, and demographic and treatment-related factors.

STUDY 3

The purpose of study 3 was to provide a comprehensive overview of socio-bureaucratic hardships faced by childhood and adolescent cancer survivors. More specifically, the aims were to describe 1) evidence on insurance, legal, and financial hardships reported by survivors and 2) risk factors associated with the respective hardships, using a systematic review.

4 METHODS

A variety of methodologies were employed across the three studies to address the aforementioned research gaps (Figure 1).

	Population and inclusion criteria	Methodology
Study 1	<i>Parental employment adjustment during and after childhood cancer treatment – a report from the Swiss Childhood Cancer Survivor Study–Parents</i>	
	Parents of long-term childhood cancer survivors Eligible for participation if <ol style="list-style-type: none"> their child was diagnosed with cancer at age ≤ 16 years their child was a Swiss resident at diagnosis ≥ 5 years have passed since diagnosis, and their child was aged ≥ 20 years in 2016 and alive 	Registry-based questionnaire study with descriptive statistics and logistic regression analyses
Study 2	<i>Attending follow-up care for childhood cancer survivors: Distance, disparities and health – a Canadian cohort study</i>	
	Survivors of childhood and adolescent cancer Eligible for inclusion if <ol style="list-style-type: none"> they were diagnosed with cancer at age ≤ 18, and ≥ 2 years have passed since treatment completion 	Cohort study linked to index data with descriptive statistics and linear, logistic, and negative binomial regression models
Study 3	<i>Insurance, legal, and financial hardships of childhood and adolescent cancer survivors – a systematic review</i>	
	Adult survivors of childhood or adolescent cancer Eligible for inclusion if <ol style="list-style-type: none"> they are adult survivors of childhood or adolescent cancer (age $\geq 16^*$) they were diagnosed with cancer at age ≤ 18 years, and ≥ 2 years have passed since diagnosis 	Systematic literature review with narrative synthesis

*Depending on the country's vocational training system, trainees may be responsible for their own social and administrative affairs before reaching the legal minimum age of 18.

Figure 1: Overview of included studies and their methodology

4.1 A registry-based questionnaire study

Patient *registries* can serve several purposes, such as monitoring clinical status, quality of life, comorbidities, and treatments of patients over time or monitoring and improving overall quality of care^{105,106}. As a data source on the presence or occurrence of a particular disease or health-related individual characteristics, they are an important data source for studies on health practices, utilization of medicines, and treatment outcomes^{105,106}.

In Switzerland, the *population-based* Childhood Cancer Registry (Kinderkrebsregister (KiKR)) records all children and adolescents diagnosed with cancer¹⁰⁷. New cases and data on the entire course of the disease and its treatment are registered in the KiKR. From January 2020, the Cancer Registration Act requires doctors and hospitals to report all cases of cancer diagnosed and treated in children and adolescents under the age of 20 to the KiKR¹⁰⁸.

Through the KiKR, parents of children who had survived cancer were recruited to participate in a larger project (Swiss Childhood Cancer Survivor Study–Parents^{13,109–112}) investigating psychosocial late outcomes in parents of long-term childhood cancer survivors using a *questionnaire survey*. Parental questionnaire data were then linked to survivor data from the registry. As part of this project, the data were analyzed to investigate the prevalence of employment changes among parents during their child’s cancer diagnosis and treatment, and whether long-term professional or financial implications were related to their child’s past illness (research question 1). Employment changes and reasons for changes were analyzed descriptively, and logistic regression analyses were conducted to predict long-term impacts.

4.2 A cohort study with index data

Cohort studies are a type of observational studies that follow a group of participants with common characteristics over time¹¹³. They are therefore particularly useful for studying health outcomes and how they are affected by certain factors, and for identifying potential risk factors and intervention possibilities.

A single-center Canadian cohort of childhood cancer survivors is being followed at the Long Term

Survivor Clinic (LTSC) at the Alberta Children’s Hospital in Calgary, Canada, from two years after treatment into adulthood. As part of their routine follow-up appointments, all survivors are asked to complete a Long Term Survivor Questionnaire (LTSQ) to assess their current health status (i.e. current reported health problems, HRQOL (anxiety, depression, pain interference, and sleep disturbance), and cancer-related fears).

Unlike perceived health status, some measures, such as measures of socio-economic inequalities, deprivation and marginalization can be difficult to assess and analyze using conventional administrative data¹¹⁴. As an alternative, area-based and geographically derived *indices* are increasingly used in social population research, including health, education and justice^{114,115}. An example of such an index is the Canadian Index of Multiple Deprivation (CIMD¹¹⁵), designed to provide a dynamic cross-sectional view of deprivation in Canada. It takes into account changes in the availability of census demographic and socio-demographic indicators and reflects current census geography. Using microdata from the Census of Population, indicators were derived at the dissemination area (i.e., the smallest standard geographic area for which all census data are disseminated) level¹¹⁵. Deprivation is depicted by four associated dimensions of deprivation: economic dependency, ethno-cultural composition, residential instability, and situational vulnerability, which all encapsule a comprehensive range of concepts. Both national and provincial/regional indices were developed¹¹⁵. Although the CIMD is a geographically based index, it can also be used as a proxy for individuals. When linked with other data, the CIMD can be used for comparisons by geographical location or by selected sub-groups¹¹⁵.

To better understand how accessible follow-up care is to childhood cancer survivors in Alberta, Canada (research question 2), a cross-sectional *cohort study* was conducted. Survivors’ travel time (proxy for clinic accessibility) to reach the clinic for long-term follow-up visits was determined using the Alberta Facilities Distance/Time Look-Up Table¹¹⁶ (developed to provide a standardized table for measurements of distances and times from postal code locations in Alberta to healthcare facilities) and Google Maps, survivors’ socio-economic situation was determined using the CIMD and health status was examined through the LTSQ. The routinely collected *questionnaire* data (LTSQ) from this

single-center Canadian cohort of childhood cancer survivors were linked to CIMD index data and travel times via survivors' postal codes. Descriptive statistics were applied to describe survivors' travel time, socio-economic situation and health status. The data was then analyzed using linear, logistic, and negative binomial regression models to examine the relationship between travel time and health status, including the role of socio-economic situation, and demographic and treatment-related factors.

4.3 A systematic literature review

Systematic literature reviews are conducted to find, select, and synthesize all available evidence on a specific topic to provide a comprehensive overview¹¹⁷. Predefined, reproducible steps complying with specific guidelines such as the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) statement¹¹⁸, are followed to ensure an unbiased, transparent and reproducible way to provide evidence for patients, healthcare providers, researchers and policy makers.

To describe what socio-bureaucratic hardships childhood cancer survivors face and who is at risk, a systematic review of existing evidence on insurance, legal, and financial hardships reported by childhood cancer survivors was undertaken (research question 3). Appropriate search blocks were created and used to search the electronic databases PubMed, CINAHL, Scopus, and PsycINFO. The databases searched were selected based on their different thematic focus to identify relevant publications from relevant areas. By covering three intertwined and mutually influencing topics within one systematic review, rather than examining them separately, we aimed to gain a better understanding of the broader picture of socio-bureaucratic hardships and their interrelated connections.

The review complies with the PRISMA guidelines¹¹⁸, and was preregistered in the Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO), an international registry with the aim of promoting transparency and open science, and preventing reporting bias and unintended duplication of studies¹¹⁹.

5 RESULTS

5.1 Parental employment adjustment during and after childhood cancer treatment – a report from the Swiss Childhood Cancer Survivor Study-Parents

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Purpose: Parents of children with cancer experience treatment-related employment disruptions. Most significant shifts occur during diagnosis and treatment. However, challenges can persist into survivorship. We explored employment changes during diagnosis and treatment among parents of children with cancer, and professional and financial impact during long-term survivorship. We investigated 1) if and what kind of employment changes occurred, 2) reasons for the changes, 3) differences between mothers and fathers, and 4) if parents experience long-term professional or financial impacts from their child's past illness.

Methods: A questionnaire survey assessed employment changes during diagnosis and treatment and long-term professional and financial impacts. We described changes and reasons thereof and conducted logistic regression analyses to predict long-term impacts.

Results: We included 469 parents (59% female) of childhood cancer survivors (mean=24 years after diagnosis). At time of treatment, 21% of parents reported employment changes: e.g., work time reduction (52%), quitting (27%), and taking unpaid leave (21%). Mothers were more likely to experience changes (OR=2.00; $p=.005$). Most parents (87%), especially mothers, reported caring for their sick child to be one of the reasons for change. Some parents reported professional (5%) or financial long-term impact (5%). Financial impact was mainly associated with survivors experiencing late effects (OR=10.51; $p<.001$), cancer relapse (OR=3.96; $p=.007$), and survivors' financial dependence (OR=3.64; $p=.005$). Professional impact was associated with female sex (OR=3.26; $p=.029$) and employment changes (OR=2.39; $p=0.050$).

Conclusions: Although most parents do not experience lasting effects on employment or finances, some continue to face challenges well into survivorship. Providing sustained, long-term support for these parents is essential.

5.2 Attending follow-up care for childhood cancer survivors: Travel time, disparities and health – a Canadian cohort study

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Submitted to Psycho-Oncology, July 2025

Objective: Despite the importance of follow-up care for childhood cancer survivors (CCS), adherence remains below recommended levels. Potential barriers include geographical distance. We aimed to improve our understanding of the accessibility of survivorship follow-up care at a Long Term Survivor Clinic (LTSC).

Methods: Questionnaire data on health status of CCS enrolled in the LTSC at the Alberta Children's Hospital in Calgary, Canada was linked to CCS' medical records and the Canadian Index of Multiple Deprivation via postal codes. Linear, logistic, and negative binomial regression models were conducted to explore the association between travel time and health status, including the role of socio-economic situation, and demographic and treatment-related factors.

Results: We included 203 CCS (48% female; mean age=23 years; mean time after diagnosis=14 years). Most CCS (75%) lived less than one hour away from the LTSC and travelled from within the province. Travel time was not significantly associated with health status. Instead, sex, time since diagnosis and certain socio-economic factors emerged as more relevant predictors. Females reported more current health problems than males (IRR=2.240; $p<.001$) and higher anxiety scores ($\beta=4.342$; $p=.010$). Socio-economic factors were associated with reporting more depressive symptoms ($\beta=4.532$; $p=.001$) and fear of second cancers (OR=2.936; $p=.009$). A more recent diagnosis was associated with fear of cancer recurrence (OR=0.878; $p=.001$) and more depressive symptoms ($\beta=-0.289$; $p=.030$).

Conclusions: Individual and socio-economic factors may play a more important role than geographic access in determining care accessibility. Providing location-appropriate services and addressing underlying socio-economic inequalities are crucial to ensuring engagement in follow-up care and improving health outcomes for CCS.

5.3 Insurance, legal, and financial hardships of childhood and adolescent cancer survivors – a systematic review

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Purpose: Childhood and adolescent cancer survivors (CACS) experience medical and psychosocial adverse effects. Attention widens to include issues such as socio-bureaucratic hardships. This systematic review synthesized the available evidence on insurance, legal, and financial hardships to better understand the broader picture of socio-bureaucratic hardships as distinct but interrelated types of hardships.

Methods: A systematic search of PubMed, Scopus, CINAHL, and PsycINFO was conducted for publications related to childhood and adolescent cancer, survivors, and insurance, legal, and financial hardships. Narrative data synthesis was performed on the extracted data.

Results: This review included $N=58$ publications, originating from 14 different countries, most from the last decade ($n=39$). We found that a considerable proportion of CACS experience insurance and financial hardships, including foregoing medical care due to financial constraints, problems paying medical bills, and difficulties accessing loans or insurances. Legal hardships, such as workplace discrimination, were less frequently investigated and reported.

Conclusions: This systematic review highlights the many interrelated socio-bureaucratic hardships faced by CACS. It is important that these hardships are not underestimated or neglected. Our findings can serve as a basis for enhancing and expanding supportive care services and help inform collaborative efforts from research, policy, and practice.

Implications for Cancer Survivors: This review emphasizes the importance of recognizing and addressing the socio-bureaucratic challenges that extend beyond medical care. Survivors should be informed about available options and be aware of their legal rights to identify instances of injustice and seek appropriate support.

6 DISCUSSION

This cumulative dissertation was conducted with the overarching objective of gaining a better understanding of the administrative, practical, and socio-bureaucratic hurdles associated with childhood cancer, with a particular focus on survivorship. The common ground across all studies discussed in this dissertation is twofold: Firstly, all findings are rooted in a diagnosis of childhood cancer. Secondly, non-medical factors play a non-negligible role in determining the course of the phase of treatment, survivorship, and the associated hardships faced by childhood cancer survivors and their parents.

6.1 Summary of main findings

The *first study*¹² aimed to better understand employment changes among parents of children with cancer during diagnosis and treatment in Switzerland, and to examine if professional and financial impacts persist long-term into survivorship. The study revealed that one-fifth of parents experienced employment changes during their child's cancer diagnosis and treatment. Treatment-related employment disruptions were more prevalent among mothers than fathers. Overall, among the parents who experienced changes, the most frequently reported changes were work time reduction, reported by over half, followed by a quarter who reported quitting, and a fifth who reported taking unpaid leave. The most commonly cited reason was a shift in caregiving responsibilities for their sick child, particularly among mothers. Some parents, again particularly mothers, as well as parents whose children were experiencing late effects, reported professional or financial impacts long after their child's diagnosis, on average more than 20 years later. Survivors' late effects were identified as one of the main determinants for parents' perceived current burden.

The *second study*'s purpose was to gain a better understanding of the accessibility of care for survivors who attend long-term follow-up care at a long-term survivor clinic in Calgary, Alberta, Canada, and to explore the contribution of travel time on survivors' health status. It was revealed that the majority of survivors lived within reasonable travel time of the clinic, with most traveling less than an hour. Travel time was not significantly associated with health status. Instead, sex, time since diagnosis, certain diagnoses and certain socio-economic factors emerged as more relevant predictors

of health status. Socio-economic factors and certain individual factors were associated with lower reported levels of HRQOL. Female survivors reported higher levels of anxiety and more current health problems.

The *third study*⁹ was a systematic review of the insurance, legal, and financial hardships experienced by childhood and adolescent cancer survivors. The aim was to synthesize the available international evidence and gain a better understanding of the broader picture of socio-bureaucratic hardships. Based on 58 included publications, the review highlighted that survivors face many long-term, interrelated socio-bureaucratic hardships, such as higher insurance premiums and deductibles due to late effects, or insurance companies excluding survivors from certain schemes or refusing to pay for medical expenses, resulting in problems with the affordability of needed care. Challenges affording necessary care, difficulties with insurance companies, and discrimination were the main problem areas described by survivors. Survivors of CNS tumors, female survivors, and those reporting low household income, unemployment, or lack of insurance seem to be most at risk for these difficulties.

6.2 Understanding the social determinants of health at play throughout the childhood cancer trajectory

The three studies demonstrate the multifaceted impact of childhood cancer on survivors' health, as well as its interplay with their and their parents' socio-economic situation and socio-bureaucratic and practical challenges. These factors, in turn, have a reciprocal influence on survivors' health and well-being, contributing to a reinforcing cycle that underscores the complex and dynamic nature of the impact of cancer on survivors and their families. The three studies show that non-medical factors play a crucial role in the survivorship experience of childhood cancer survivors and their parents.

These non-medical factors – personal, social, and environmental aspects that influence well-being and health outcomes can be referred to as *social determinants of health* (SDOH). The World Health Organization (WHO) broadly defines SDOH as “the conditions in which people are born, grow, work, live, and age, and people’s access to power, money and resources”¹²⁰. SDOH significantly impact health inequalities, the unjust and avoidable differences in health status that exist both within and

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between countries^{120,121}. Across countries, health and illness follow a social gradient, at all income levels: The lower the person's socio-economic position, the worse their health¹²⁰, disproportionately impacting already vulnerable groups.

According to Healthy People 2030, SDOH can be grouped into five key domains: (1) *economic stability*, (2) *educational access and quality*, (3) *healthcare access and quality*, (4) *neighborhood and built environment*, and (5) *social and community context*¹²². Within each domain, there are underlying factors. Factors within the *economic stability* domain are stable housing, food security, stable employment, and poverty. *Educational access and quality* includes early childhood education, high school graduation, literacy, and higher education enrollment. *Healthcare access and quality* takes into account people's access to healthcare and primary care and health literacy. Access to healthy foods, crime and violence, environment conditions, and housing quality are factors in the *neighborhood and built environment* domain. *Social and community context* considers social cohesion, incarceration, civic participation, and discrimination^{37,122}.

Contemplating the challenges identified in this dissertation, it can be seen that they fall into the aforementioned five key domains of the SDOH. These challenges place a burden on a group that is already vulnerable due to childhood cancer and its late effects, potentially further impacting their health through non-medical factors, i.e., SDOH. Some SDOH are present before a cancer diagnosis, such as a child's ethnicity, a parent's sex, or a family's socio-economic status, potentially contributing to delayed diagnoses and poorer survival rates^{31,32,37}. Others may become imminent through cancer itself or may be exacerbated by the late effects of cancer and its treatment, like a disability or an increased risk for unemployment and financial hardship⁹.

To understand how the different types of SDOH can lead to disparate outcomes for diverse populations, intersectionality is crucial¹²¹. Intersectionality emphasizes that different dimensions of social identities and structures are interconnected¹²¹. It highlights how factors such as sex, ethnicity, race, socio-economic status, sexual orientation, and disability status are intertwined, resulting in distinct advantages or disadvantages. These include an individual's access to resources, opportunities, and healthcare services¹²¹. This cumulative dissertation, with the three included studies helped to

show how this is the case for childhood cancer patients, survivors and their parents. Figure 2 depicts the non-medical challenges that affect families throughout the cancer trajectory.

These various determinants and associated challenges can delay or prevent progress in various areas of life. Depending on where a family or survivor is on the cancer continuum, they may have a greater or lesser impact on outcomes as well as support needs.

6.3 Access to care, support, and the social security system

As revealed in the included studies, access to appropriate care and support systems is not granted to everyone, even in countries with a high SDI. While study 2 suggests that at least geographical location might not be as big of an influence on health outcomes for survivors attending LTFU care, study 3 shows that gaps persist in accessibility of care through socio-bureaucratic factors. This is, for instance, shown by survivors forgoing or skipping needed care because of costs⁹. Insurance coverage affects survivors' ability to access follow-up care⁹¹, and receiving preventive health services^{9,123}.

However, as survivors are at an elevated risk of chronic health conditions^{1,61} and might need to use healthcare services more frequently in the long term¹²⁴, difficulties with affordability of care make them an even more vulnerable population⁹. Therefore, once needs and risks have been identified, it is essential to ensure that appropriate care and support are available and accessible to those who need it. Access to care that addresses both health and socio-bureaucratic risks can optimize the achievement of independent living and working, as well as access to insurance²⁵.

Geographical location is not the only factor that determines accessibility to care. Socio-economic and individual factors also play a role. As shown in study 2, socio-economic situation impacts health status. Better health status, in turn, can be influenced by attending follow-up care^{7,60}. Attending follow-up care, however, can be both time- and resource-consuming, if transportation expenses, food on the way, or accommodation for staying overnight must be borne¹²⁵. This is particularly detrimental to vulnerable families, who are disproportionately affected.

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Figure 2: The long shadow of childhood cancer: Non-medical determinants throughout the childhood cancer trajectory

In Switzerland, every resident must be affiliated to and is covered by basic health insurance^{126,127}.

Furthermore, the country operates a close-knit network of different types of social insurance schemes, that offer persons working or living in Switzerland, and their family members, broad protection against risks with financial consequences not covered by conventional insurance¹²⁸. The Swiss social security system includes, among other schemes, disability insurance (DI), or income compensation allowances when caring for a seriously ill child^{128,129}.

The continuation of employment during treatment can affect parents' employment situation after the end of treatment¹³⁰. As shown in study 1, predominantly mothers give up or reduce their paid work and are the ones more likely to report long-term professional impacts because of their child's illness. Previous research found that parents face difficulties when returning to or finding employment due to their caregiving role, with some employers perceiving the ongoing care needs of a child with cancer as a disadvantage⁴⁶. Mothers, in particular, encounter significant challenges, frequently also as a result of their own health issues stemming from the emotional toll of being the primary caregiver during treatment⁴⁶. Although they do not regret prioritizing their child's care, many mothers later recognize the long-term sacrifices to their careers and financial stability. They express concerns about their future and regret over becoming financially dependent on their partners⁴⁶.

In a Swedish focus group study, parents explain that support systems, such as public and private insurance, healthcare services, and financial help from family and friends, allowed them to prioritize caring for their child over work⁴⁶. Parents who participated in study 1 were only entitled to three days of paid care leave under the Swiss Code of Obligations¹²⁹. Since 2021, however, working parents in Switzerland can claim up to 14 weeks of care leave, receiving a daily allowance equivalent to 80% of their salary, to care for children with severe health impairments, in accordance with the Income Compensation Ordinance (EO)^{129,131}. Given the complex and treatment-intensive nature of childhood cancer, 14 weeks may be insufficient, and the potentially long-term care needs of children with late effects are also not taken into account. It is important to recognize the long-term impact of parenting a child with cancer⁴⁶.

Not only parents, but also survivors are considered in the social security system in Switzerland. In order for survivors to receive disability insurance benefits and/or supplementary benefits in Switzerland, they must submit a claim in their canton of residence¹²⁸. Social security systems are an important mechanism and may offer alleviation. However, complicated application processes, uncertainty regarding qualifications, and stigma associated with being a DI-recipient, impede obtaining support¹³².

6.4 Comprehensive (follow-up) care: Screening for needs

It is important not only to ensure that care and support are available and accessible, but also to ensure that they are targeted at where they are needed and tailored to the needs of those affected. As the three studies showed, survivors and their parents face difficulties in various areas.

As survivors' outcomes are also influenced by their parents' situation, evaluation of needs and risk factors should start with the parents. As shown in study 1, many parents face employment disruptions and changes during the treatment and diagnosis of their child, impacting some into long-term survivorship. Screening families' needs throughout the cancer trajectory and re-assessing potential for support is crucial. As revealed in study 1, long-term financial impact is significantly associated with having a child with late effects or a cancer relapse. Mothers and parents who experienced employment changes at the time of diagnosis and treatment were more likely to report a long-term professional impact during the survivorship phase. This suggests that certain parents and families may be at greater risk for financial or professional difficulties. Screening at-risk families for needs could help prevent or ease certain long-term consequences.

In collaboration with an interdisciplinary team of experts and stakeholders, a group of pediatric oncology psychosocial professionals, has developed 15 evidence- and consensus-based standards for pediatric psychosocial cancer care¹³³. In addition to routine assessments of psychosocial needs and psychoeducation, information and guidance on acute and long-term consequences for parents and those affected, the standards also include support for reintegration into school and assessments of the risk of financial difficulties¹³³. The standards further call for routine, systematic assessment of the

psychosocial healthcare needs of youth with cancer and their families¹³³. According to the model, all families should have access to support, but the focus should be on those families who need it most. Psychosocial education should be provided to everyone, as should screening for risk factors¹³³. Survivorship care should ideally be expanded to also cover socio-bureaucratic areas and prepare parents and survivors for potential hardships and where to find appropriate support.

Although screening for psychosocial risks and SDOH is recognized as important for guiding the delivery of resources, identifying and implementing effective, evidence-based methods of doing both simultaneously remains a critical challenge^{134,135}. One suggestion for an assessment to be used is the Psychosocial Assessment Tool (PAT), an evidence-based screening tool for family psychosocial risk. Based on the social ecology framework, it covers significant aspects of SDOH and may augment the assessment of SDOH with including items important to the pediatric healthcare setting¹³⁴. With a particular focus on families at risk for disparities and on key transition points, support should be offered continuously.

The widespread integration of SDOH screening into oncological care would help to identify patients, survivors and families who are at risk in socio-bureaucratic areas and enable targeted support services to be provided. Critical resources such as financial support for transport costs or counseling on finances, insurance, and legal matters would help to close or at least reduce gaps. Navigating support systems and dealing with complex paperwork has been described as burdening and overwhelming¹⁰. Survivors' have unmet needs in these regards and voice strong needs for support with legal questions and concerns regarding insurance¹³², however support is often lacking, leaving survivors feeling alone and overwhelmed^{9,136-138}. Study 3 showed that hardships in the areas of insurance, legal issues, and finances often stem from bureaucratic hurdles, regulations, or complicated systems, calling for socio-bureaucratic support and information to be provided to survivors throughout the entire cancer trajectory⁹. To give survivors more weight when, for instance, dealing with bureaucratic issues such as insurance or disability insurance applications, comprehensive screening for (late) complications in all areas would also help to document late effects attributable to cancer more effectively. However, as shown in study 3, insurance, legal, and financial hardships are often investigated as secondary

outcomes and not always systematically assessed. Often surveyed in routinely applied questionnaires are income, employment, insurance status, and socio-economic status, but socio-bureaucratic hardships are surveyed to a lesser extent⁹.

Standardized survivorship care ensures early detection and treatment or prevention of late effects^{7,60}. Certain late effects require educational approaches and guidance, while others require monitoring strategies, such as diagnostic tests and screenings²⁵. Most guidelines for ensuring standardized and routinized screenings focus primarily on physical late effects^{26,67,139}. However, screening is also particularly important for psychosocial late effects, practical needs and late effects in the socio-bureaucratic sphere. As shown in study 3, many survivors face long-term insurance, legal, and financial hardships⁹. Screening for these early on, for instance, at important transition points, especially in survivors at risk, namely survivors of CNS tumors, female survivors, and those reporting low household income, unemployment, or lack of insurance⁹, could help alleviate or even prevent these hardships.

6.5 Stages in the cancer survivorship trajectory: Critical transition points

As the three studies in this dissertation showed, each stage of the cancer trajectory presents unique challenges. This includes critical transition points throughout the different stages of cancer care and survivorship. Corresponding support needs undergo a shift over time. Consequently, it is of the utmost importance to provide parents, patients, and survivors with continuous information and adequate support appropriate to their needs.

End of treatment and returning to everyday life

During treatment, the focus lies on survival and “getting through”⁴. Caring for the sick child is parents’ main priority. Professional responsibilities may be given up and new parental roles emerge⁴¹. With the treatment coming to an end, a new unknown takes over. The transition from active cancer treatment to survivorship is a time of mixed emotions for survivors and their families^{140,141}. While treatment completion is often associated with great relief, leaving the protected environment of the hospital and its staff can come with uncertainty^{4,140,142}. Re-establishing roles, returning to work, and

resuming family life can be challenging and confusing¹⁴³. In contrast to the active treatment phase, families describe a sudden reduction in psychosocial and practical support from their oncology healthcare team, leaving them feeling unsupported and abandoned^{146,141,142,144}. For survivors, the transition often involves efforts to regain a sense of “normalcy”, such as reintegrating into school and reconnecting with friends. However, many report a discrepancy between their expectations for life after treatment and the reality they encounter¹⁴¹. Many also experience struggling with changes in physical appearance and ongoing health concerns¹⁴².

Handing over responsibility for health to survivors

As described in study 1, parents assume the primary responsibility for their child’s health and organizational matters during the treatment period and the initial phase of survivorship. At some point during survivorship, there is a transition phase towards greater personal responsibility taken on by the survivors themselves. This encompasses knowing about one’s health history, managing appointments and attending LTFU care, and keeping all the health information and documents together. Some survivors describe finding it difficult to recall their cancer diagnosis, partly due to their young age at diagnosis and the time that has passed since treatment¹⁴⁵. Others attribute this to caregivers and medical teams withholding information and making decisions without involving them, leading survivors to learn about their illness second-hand from caregivers¹⁴⁵. Tools such as the Survivorship Passport¹⁴⁶ (comparable to the Passport for Care¹⁴⁷), can support and simplify health information management. Through a secure website, a patient’s medical history after cancer treatment can be accessed which helps both survivors and healthcare professionals understand potential late effects and risks¹⁴⁶.

With the transition to adulthood, insurance coverage and benefits may change, as survivors move from family to individual plans or, depending on the country, between public and private systems¹⁴⁸. As study 3 showed, challenges with socio-bureaucratic matters such as handling insurance claims, applying for disability insurance, or navigating financial hardships are common among childhood cancer survivors. Survivors are at increased risk of forgoing or delaying necessary care because of

costs, especially when uninsured^{90,149}, leaving them vulnerable to lapses in care that could jeopardize early detection or prevention of late effects⁸¹.

Transition from pediatric to adult follow-up care

Between the ages of 18 and 21, it is recommended that survivors transition from pediatric- to adult-based healthcare settings for their medical care¹⁵⁰. This transition is critical to ensure that guideline-based follow-up care is continued to mitigate the impact of late effects and screen for secondary conditions and cancers¹⁵¹. However, the proportion of survivors reporting survivor-focused care that comprises regular risk-based surveillance and prevention strategies decreases with increasing time from cancer²⁵, indicating that for many, the transition to adult-based survivorship care is unsuccessful^{152,153}.

Transition phases are critical and can determine the course of survivorship. The transition points carry the potential risk of 'losing' survivors and families, and the risk of no longer being able to offer the necessary support and guarantee the requisite care. Research shows that with increasing time since diagnosis, adult survivors are harder to locate and engage in follow-up care, once lost^{154,155}. Re-assessing needs in all areas for each of these phases for both parents and survivors is crucial.

6.6 Implications for research and practice

While the three studies within this dissertation have added to the existing literature, they have also revealed research gaps and potential for expansion of support and system-level interventions to help progress long-term comprehensive and continuous care for all childhood cancer survivors and their families.

To date, various interventions aimed at helping survivors and their families cope with and adapt to childhood cancer have been developed. However, rigorous evidence on their effectiveness is lacking and only few are systematically implemented into routine care^{8,156}. A national survey of pediatric oncology social workers in the United States revealed several areas for improvement, including the following: funding for psychosocial support staff and programs, incorporation of standardized assessment measures, consistent access to psychology and psychiatry, integration of care for parents

and siblings, and assessment of financial burden throughout treatment and beyond¹⁵⁶. Australian healthcare professionals recognize the importance of addressing financial concerns in routine cancer care, but note that it is often considered a “blind spot” within the medical model, due to barriers such as limited services, resources, and training¹⁵⁷. As demonstrated, critical transition points bear the risk of losing families and survivors to appropriate support. As described earlier, parents report that after leaving the hospital environment, they often feel left alone and overwhelmed¹⁴⁴, and it is often only after the end of the child’s treatment that parents become aware of the repercussions for themselves^{46,143}. Contacting families after they have left the hospital, once they have had time to adjust to their new situation, to offer appropriate support services or assistance, could help reach parents at a time when they are more receptive to offers of help and guidance.

In this context, one question that arises is how this could best be implemented. At the same time, it should be noted that comprehensive care, possibly even beyond the treatment period, requires time, resources, and expertise in addition to the already intensive medical care provided¹³⁵. Structures within hospitals would either have to be expanded to address practical needs and socio-bureaucratic issues with families, or ways would have to be found to better connect families and survivors with existing resources and services offered by the established social services sector outside the healthcare system¹³⁵. While services are available, their outreach to potentially eligible families could be enhanced. In Switzerland, for instance, several foundations and organizations are dedicated to helping families affected by cancer and have expanded their services accordingly¹³. Nevertheless, certain needs remain unmet, or assistance is hindered by administrative complexities or unclear guidelines^{13,56}. In a Swiss study, over half of the questioned parents said that they would make use of a contact point for questions regarding health insurance, disability insurance, or legal basics, and that they wished for a permanent contact person¹³. If this person is introduced to families during their hospital stay or shortly after, this approach has the added benefit of preventing potential gaps in care after leaving the protected hospital environment and lowering the threshold for accessing financial support services, for example, not only during but also after the treatment phase. Parents could also be contacted during their child's survivorship to draw their attention to critical socio-bureaucratic

transitions, such as reaching the legal age or early clarification with disability insurance. They could also be more easily invited to information events or community activities with other parents. This could, in turn, facilitate the transfer of information about support services to survivors, integrating them into a support system outside of follow-up care as soon as they take on greater responsibility for their health and administrative matters related to their past cancer, reducing the risk of “losing” them. Where appropriate, telemedicine could serve as an accessible and cost-effective alternative or supplement.

Supporting transitions more carefully could help ensure engagement and adherence, especially when it comes to long-term follow-up and the transition from the pediatric to the adult care setting. This transition has been defined as an “active, planned, coordinated, comprehensive, multidisciplinary process to enable childhood and adolescent cancer survivors to effectively and harmoniously transfer from child-centered to adult-oriented healthcare systems”^{158,159}. However, this often comes with challenges. The transition can be facilitated depending on the setup of clinic processes and collaboration between the pediatric and adult healthcare systems. As a recent systematic review has identified, there is no single-best model of transitional care, and literature describing transition practices is limited¹⁵⁸. Some models that are being described include survivors beginning gradual preparation for transition to adult care years before the actual transition occurs. A transition nurse navigator who is employed by both institutions provides support and education to survivors to help navigate the new healthcare system^{81,160}.

Aimed at improving survivors’ health insurance literacy and corresponding financial hardship, promising interventions, such as the health insurance navigation tool (HINT¹⁶¹) intervention, are being developed and tested to target survivors’ healthcare and medical needs¹⁶¹. In four sessions the HINT intervention is delivered synchronously by a patient navigator and a corresponding booklet. The sessions include psychoeducation about health insurance policy and coverage in the context of survivorship care, with a focus on overcoming barriers to insurance access and use, but also training and support for survivors to empower them to challenge coverage denials or seek lower-cost

alternatives¹⁶¹. This could help alleviate or even prevent socio-bureaucratic burdens, as survivors would be more adequately prepared and receive long-term support.

In a Swiss study, legal and insurance experts emphasize the need for interdisciplinary support for socio-economic aspects as part of survivors' follow-up care¹³². While acknowledging that their recommendations do not supersede medical advice, they contend that healthcare professionals likewise should refrain from making legal, social insurance, or employment law judgments. On occasion, such extra-medical advice can result in legal misinformation being submitted to survivors, which can be difficult to rectify when it is provided by healthcare professionals¹³².

Other research suggests that survivors should make their own choice for their long-term follow-up provider and states that a successful model of long-term follow-up care needs the flexibility to adapt to the survivors' individual needs^{138,139,162}. Experts recommend that here as well, a coordinator of care or key worker could be put in place to empower survivors to make their own decisions^{139,162}. Shared decision-making, digital support tools, and tailored communication are suggested to help survivors stay engaged in follow-up care and underscore the need for a patient-centered approach that honors individual preferences while promoting long-term health and well-being⁶⁴.

However, as this dissertation and the three included papers show, in addition to targeted and tailored interventions, system-level interventions and possible systematic changes cannot be ruled out. One legislative measure adopted by several European countries is the establishment of the "Right to Be Forgotten"¹⁶³⁻¹⁶⁵. This legal provision requires EU member states to prohibit the use of cancer-related health data when individuals apply for insurance, once a certain period has passed since the end of treatment¹⁶³⁻¹⁶⁵. Consequently, survivors are no longer required to disclose their cancer history to insurers¹⁶³.

The implementation of such policies represents a significant step toward reducing the risk of discrimination faced by survivors and could improve ensured access to care. Addressing inequalities in the care of childhood cancer survivors requires policy-driven solutions. It is further necessary that all relevant parties acknowledge the long-term implications of parenting a child with cancer⁴⁶. A

coordinated support system, encompassing major stakeholders, such as healthcare, social security systems, welfare agencies, and employers is imperative. Applying collaborative efforts from research, policy, and practice is crucial due to the interdependence of issues and due to the complexity of systems.

6.7 Limitations and strengths

Beyond the individual strengths and limitations discussed in the three studies included in this dissertation, the dissertation itself has its own strengths and limitations. By bringing together research about different populations (survivors and parents), as well as different time points on the cancer continuum (from the time of diagnosis and treatment to long-term survivorship), challenges throughout the cancer trajectory and beyond survivorship could be explored and integrated into the framework of SDOH. This dissertation provides important impulses for future research. However, to fully explore the scale of non-medical factors at play further research is needed to formulate sustainable recommendations and concrete interventions. Although childhood cancer is rare, interventions could benefit a broader range of people due to rising survival rates and implications for other serious childhood diseases.

Another strength of this dissertation is that it draws on a broad data basis by applying different methodologies and using different data sources. Despite this, the majority of the evidence that informs the conclusions drawn in this dissertation is based on countries with a high SDI, leading to limited generalizability. However, as these disparities exist even in countries with high SDI and countries with universal healthcare, this dissertation demonstrates that in countries with lower SDI, where socio-economic differences are most likely to be even greater, conducting further research in both disparities at time of diagnosis and treatment but also later in survivorship is urgent to identify possibilities for interventions. Interventions must be adapted to the specific system of a country, which limits the generalizability of certain interventions. Conversely, this approach offers the opportunity to explore a variety of methods and select the most appropriate ones for implementation in different systems.

7 CONCLUSION

Childhood cancer survivors and their parents encounter numerous challenges, which extend beyond the realms of physical and psychological well-being. This dissertation highlights that socio-bureaucratic hardships, practical needs and barriers to care and support are prominent among the challenges associated with surviving childhood cancer. The findings highlight the multifaceted impact of childhood cancer on survivors' health and its complex interaction with both their own and their parents' socio-economic circumstances, as well as with socio-bureaucratic and practical challenges. These factors, in turn, have a reciprocal influence on survivors' health and well-being, contributing to a reinforcing cycle that underscores the complex and dynamic nature of the impact of cancer on survivors and their families.

At each stage of the childhood cancer trajectory, these non-medical factors have been demonstrated to play a non-negligible role in determining the course of treatment, survivorship and the associated hardships faced by survivors and their parents. This dissertation advocates for the provision of appropriate, targeted, and continuous support in all areas of need, and calls for collaborative efforts between researchers, policymakers and practitioners to address these issues.

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